

1. Field layout showing wind break double wall and colonization of adult BPH on plants in cylindrical cages. Cuttack, India.

2. BPH hopperburn in field planted test entries. Cuttack, India.

test entry with 2 rows of susceptible Jaya or TN1 on each side. Surface foliar sprays of 0.02% methyl parathion are applied weekly between 10 and 60 DAP to kill natural enemies. At transplanting, seedlings are dipped in the same solution.

Hopperburn appeared in patches by 80 DAP and by 95 DAP reached 100% in the susceptible check (Fig. 2). Monitoring data of insect buildup at weekly intervals showed that by 75 DAP 6 BPH adults, 75 BPH nymphs, and 1 mirid bug were present on each hill. Between 90 and 100 DAP, BPH adults and nymphs exceeded 500/hill. Beyond 80 DAP, hopperburn spread so fast that insect populations became irrelevant. BPH populations emigrated from the plots by 100 DAP.

In 1983, 10 known resistant cultures, IR36, and susceptible Ratna were evaluated. Based on percent hopperburned hills (see table), CR401-7, CR233-10, CR157-1900, and CR157-380-303 were on par and were outstandingly superior to IR36 in field resistance.

In 1984, CR333-6-1 was outstanding among 50 entries, followed by CR316-639, CR319-644, CR233-10, CR157-212, CR157-300, and CR157-1900, which were on par with the resistant check CR57-MR1523.

Because percent hopperburned hills in a test entry was recorded only when check entries were 100% hopperburned, single-replication testing appeared acceptable, which saves valuable resources. □

Relative performance of some rice cultivars under induced field outbreak of BPH, CRRI, 1983 dry season.^a

Cultivar	Cross combination	Mean hopperburned hills ^a	
		%	Angles
CR407-6-2	CR94-1512-6/Ratna	92 d	76.85
CR407-19	CR94-1512-6/Ratna	100 de	90.00
CR157-392-212	Vijaya/PTB10	68 ab	56.06
CR157-1900	Vijaya/PTB10	54 ab	47.32
CR157-380-303	Vijaya/PTB10	57 ab	49.25
CR404-56	CR94-1512-6/Pusa-2-21	95 de	82.79
CR233-10	Pelita/CR94-MR.1550	48 a	44.07
CR57-11-2	IR8/PTB21	59 ab	50.76
CR401-7	Vijaya/CR94-1512-6	45 a	42.40
CR190-103	CR129-118/CR57-49-2	61 ab	51.75
IR36		87 bc	71.98
Ratna (susceptible check)		100 de	90.00
	CD (0.05)		16.08
	CD (0.01)		21.86

^aMean of 3 replications. Separation of mean (angles) in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Evaluation of promising rice varieties for thrips resistance

Zhu Zhao-qi and Li Yi Wei, Plant Protection Research Institute, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing, China

Thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) is a major rice pest along the lower Changjiang River in China. Seedlings of the second rice crop often are damaged in Jun-Jul. We developed the following scale for evaluating thrips resistance.

Rating	Damage
1	No rolling of terminal of leaf; a few silvery spots on leaf surfaces.

- 3 Rolling of leaf terminals; light silvery of leaf tips.
- 5 Rolling of leaf terminals; yellow-reddish and scorched leaf tips.
- 7 Rolling of entire length of all leaves with pronounced rigidity.
- 9 All plants dead.

Seventy-five thrips-resistant rice varieties from IRRI were evaluated at Wu-Jiang district in Jiangsu Province. The varieties were sown on 10 and 15 Jun 1984. About 100 seeds of each entry were sown in moist soils in a 0.5-m-long row at 0.250 m row spacing. One week later, fields were flooded to a proper level.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of the test varieties were evaluated using the

scale. Of 75 entries, 6 scored 1; 3, 3; 59, 5; and 7, 7 (see table). The six most resistant entries were from Sri Lanka. □

Thrips resistance rating of rice varieties, Jiangsu, China.

Reaction rating	Variety name ^a
1	Dahanala (15663), Dahanala 682 (50729), Kalubalawee (7717 & 15184), Kalu Heenati (15745 & 31431).
3	Kaluheenati (7750), Madael (15234), Wannu Dahanala (11726).
5	ADT22 (5901), ASD4 (5814), ASD7 (6303), Balamawe (15276), BJ1 (256, 3711, & 45195), BW78 (26915), Chandina (36420), CO 23 (6042), CO 27 (26843), Dahanala (15202 & 15650), Demala Kotan (40787), Gangala (7733, 15207, & 15259), Gona-baru (7809), H105 (158), Heenati (8964), Herath Banda (15304, 15362, 15378, 15632, 15748, 31412, & 31431), Jeeraga Samba (49732), Kalubalawee (7702), Kaluheenati (11996), Kalu Heenati (15568, 31432, 31433, 31434, 31435, 36267, & 36268), Kaohsiung Sen Yu 185 (38892), Madael (7722, 7727, 11701, & 15426), MRC 505 (39519), Perunel (15473), Ptb 33 (19325), Sinna Sivappu (15444), Sudu Hondarawala (15541), Suduru Samba (11671, 15237, 15272, & 36390), Sudurvi 305 (3475), Thunmar hamara (15226), TKM 2 (6034), TKM 6 (237, 6216, 35185), TNR 1 (9913), Utri Rajapan (16684).
7	Kuribit Puti (26882), Nira (1749, & 6309), Suduru Samba (14354), Sugadas (or Godavari Samba 50163), TKM6 (28571), Wulan Rua (19194).
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^aIRRI accession no. are in parentheses.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization COLD TOLERANCE

VL Dhan 16: a medium-maturing, cold-tolerant rice for irrigated conditions

V. S. Chauhan and J. C. Bhatt, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture, Almora 263601, India

We evaluated many advanced breeding lines to identify a suitable cold-tolerant variety for irrigated valleys at 900 m to 1,500 m altitudes. Some selections from IR1846 (J. P. 5/Y. R. L. I) were promising. One selection performed well in regional and national trials. It was released by the State Varietal Release Committee in 1984 as VL Dhan 16.

VL Dhan 16 is medium tall, compact, and stiff-strawed with medium tillering and light green leaves. Panicles are long and compact with good spikelet fertility and threshability. The husk and apiculus are straw-colored. Grains are medium-

Grain yield of VL Dhan 16 in multilocal trials, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	1980 (2)	1981 (4)	1982 (4)	1983 (4)	Mean
VL Dhan 16	4.3	5.4	4.5	4.2	4.6
VL 8	4.3	3.7	3.2	2.8	3.5
VLK 39	3.6	3.9	3.4	2.5	3.4
Thapachini	3.5	3.8	3.8	2.8	3.5

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate test locations.

sized with red kernels, nonglutinous endosperm, and good cooking quality. VL Dhan 16 has good blast and stem borer resistance and is cold tolerant.

In 14 multilocal yield trials during 4 yr, VL Dhan 16 was compared with VL-8 (improved medium-maturity check), VLK 39 (improved early check), and Thapachini (a local check) (see table). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Salinity and sodicity tolerance in rice

A. Qadar, Division of Genetics and Plant Physiology, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, Haryana, India

In a study of salinity and sodicity tolerance in rice, 40-d-old M1-48 seedlings were transplanted in pots in soils with EC 2.8, 7.0, 11.2, or 15.9 dS/m and pH 8.2, 9.5, 9.8, or 10.0. Exchangeable sodium

1. Effect of salinity (a) and sodicity (b) on percent reduction of grain yield and Na⁺ content of mature shoots of M1-48.